

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 4 |
April 2022 | Monthly Journal by
TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly peer reviewed Journal by **The
World Association of Scientists &
Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Basic Factors Affecting the Project Success among Industrial Companies in Yemen

Abdullah Abduljlil Shaalan Dahan Al-boraihi ^{1*}, Guo Bin ^{2*}, Hashem Musaed Ahmed Al-Qarwaei ³, Hesham Mohammed Mohammed Hasan Al-yaaburi ⁴

¹ Postgraduate Student, Department of economic and management, Taiyuan University of Technology

² Professor, Department of economic and management, Taiyuan University of Technology

³ Postgraduate Student, Department of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology

⁴ Department of Commerce, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University

Accepted April 12,2022

Published April 28,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

*Corresponding Author: Abdullah Abduljlil Shaalan Dahan Al-boraihi, Guo Bin

Funding: None

How to cite this article: Abdullah Abduljlil Shaalan Dahan Al-boraihi, Guo Bin, Hashem Musaed Ahmed Al-Qarwaei , Hesham Mohammed Mohammed Hasan Al-yaaburi (2022). Basic Factors Affecting the Project Success among Industrial Companies in Yemen. *North American Academic Research*, 5(4), 132-143. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6499023>

ABSTRACT

The reason for this study is to examine the basic factors that impact a successful project among industrial companies in Yemen. In expansion, this study is additionally pointed to investigate in case of project alter control play a part in directing the relationship between the independent factors and dependent variable distinguished in this investigation. Through the writing audit preparation, it was found that project mission, best administration back, client discussion, specialized mission, personnel competency, client acknowledgment, inconvenience shooting, project arrange observing and successful communication are among the basic factors distinguished. The primary data of this study was collected by questionnaire, this questionnaire was designed and distributed to respondents by several ways like email, fax, post, social media such as WhatsApp and Facebook and hand by hand to some of respondents, the 67 respondents only who reacted to 67 effectively completed projects. This study revealed that project success within the industrial setting was in two measurements which this study classified as smaller scale and large scale project success. This study is illustrated experimentally that project staff competency and project mission are basic factors impacting the small scale project success and as for large scale project success, best administration bolster and project mission are two fundamental basic factors.

Keywords

Basic factors, project success, industrial companies, administration, Yemen.

Introduction

Project administration as an administration teaches underpins much financial action. In businesses as different as an industry, projects drive trade. Project management, in this manner, is emphasized as the method of making choices and operationalizing certain techniques and tactics to bring the project to success. Concurring to Mobey and Parker (2002), to extend the chances of a project succeeding it is vital for the organization to have an understanding of what are the basic success factors, to efficiently and quantitatively assess these basic factors, foreseeing conceivable impacts, and after that select suitable strategy of managing with them. once recognized, the success of the project can be carried out. Large-scale building and development ventures have customarily overwhelmed the subject of project management and usage.

Concurring to Pinto (1986), the project usage preparation is complex, as a rule, requires broad and collective consideration to a wide perspective of a human, budgetary and specialized factors. In expansion, projects regularly have a specialized set of basic success factors in which in case tended to and consideration is given will progress the probability of effective usage. On the other hand on the off chance that these factors were not taken genuinely might lead to the disappointment of the project. Commerce nowadays is working beneath a large level of instability, projects usage is open to all sorts of outside impact, unforeseen occasions, ever-growing necessities, changing imperatives, and fluctuating asset streams. This clearly appears that on the off chance that projects are connected and steps are not taken in arrange to manage them successfully and proficiently, the chances of disappointment are high. Based on the measurements distributed by the Yemeni Mechanical Improvement Specialist in September 2016, the number of affirmed industrial projects has expanded by over 20% in the year 2011. These affirmed industrial projects summed to an add-up to a capital investment of over YER 40 billion in 2015 and YER 55 billion in 2016 from both nearby and remote investments, an increment of 10% from the past year. 50% were effectively executed and generally comprised generation and machine establishment projects, though 50.7% was in dynamic arranging arrange (MIDA, 2006).

The projects are being utilized broadly within the industry; it is in this manner imperative to recognize factors that contribute to the successful implementation of the project. This is often too bolstered by an observational think about conducted by Belassi and Tukel (1996) where industrial respondents accounted for 40.7% of the full respondents in which item advancement projects were most common. Appropriately, this paper is to distinguish the basic factors that contribute to project success in the industrial division in Yemen. This paper hence starts with an outline of the project's success. Taking after this outline, an introduction to basic factors for project success should be talked about. This paper moreover presents the technique utilized within considering. Typically taken after by the investigation and in conclusion and suggestions might be discussed.

Basic factors for project success

Creating or recognizable proof of success factors has ruled the field of project administration from the 1990s to 2000. Numerous analysts have attempted to a certain degree to distinguish success factors for project administration. Amongst analysts like Pinto and Slevin (1989), Clarke (1999), Cooke Davis (2002) and Muller and Turner (2003),. The taking after para-charts is committed to investigating the most donors in setting the success factors. To summarize the results from the literature review, indicate to Table 1, which organizes the success factors that were recognized by distinctive analysts (Pinto and Slevin, 1987; Wateridge, 1995; Belassi and Tukel, 1996; Cooke-Davis, 2002; and Muller, 2003). The calculate records shift from wide common traces to a particular point of thought.

From the literature review, it is reported that Pinto's inquired about in 1986 and his ensuing results with Slevin on their results of 10 basic success factors have since got to be a classic piece of works in this field. Their illustration is one of the foremost broadly cited records of basic success factors (Muller and Turner, 2005). This proposed consider will take advantage of this classic work and will further create it within the setting of industrial companies. For this reason, the 10-factor procedure model of project administration as built up by Pinto (1986) should be embraced for this study. Be that as it may other than the ten basic success factors embraced from Pinto (1986), this study has moreover extended the factor of staff to cover the administration framework and competency of the project pioneer, on the project success based on the bolster of the literature review highlighted within the prior part.

Hypotheses of study

This study has several hypotheses that have been defined to test the relationship between both the independent factors and dependent variables.

H1: High bolster from the best administration is strongly related to project success in industrial companies.

H2: Recurrent and high client discussions are strongly related to project success in industrial companies.

H3: specialized tasks are strongly related to project success in industrial companies.

H4: High client approval is strongly related to project success in industrial companies.

H5: Competent project staff is strongly related to the project success in industrial companies

H6: Recurrent checking and feedback action is positively related to project success in industrial companies.

H7: Successful and suitable communication is strongly related to project success in industrial companies.

Success of project

Progressively these days companies are project-based, meaning that the work they do is part of programs of projects outlined to convey the company's methodologies and include esteem. Great administration of these projects is fundamental on the off chance that the company is progressing to succeed. Equally important to a person's project success is guaranteeing that the correct projects are carried out. As project administration guru Bob Buttrick puts it, "Coordinating the person project accurately will guarantee it is done right". Coordinating

all the projects effectively will ensure we are doing the correct projects." Success is a curious word and a word that's so common and wide that it is troublesome to characterize and get shared understanding when inquired from a diverse person.

Jugdev and Muller (2005) in their study stated that in arrange to characterize what success implies in a project setting is like picking up an agreement from a bunch of individuals on the definition of "good art." Project success may be a theme that's as often as possible talked about and however seldom concurred upon (Baccarini, 1999). By and enormous, the views on project success have advanced over a long time from straightforward definitions that were restricted to the execution stage of the extended life cycle to definitions that reflect an appreciation of success over the whole project and item life cycle (Jugdev and Muller, 2005).

Table 1. Summary of literature reviews on basic factors for success of project.

Factors of Success from the Literature review	Pinto (1986)	Pinto & Slevin (1989)	Belassi & Tukul (1996)	Wateridge (1995)	Belout (1998)	Clarke (1999)	Cooke-Davies	Muller (2005)
Corporate understanding		✓		✓				
Organizational adaptability	✓	✓		✓				
Communication								
Project supervisor determination criteria	✓	✓				✓		
Project supervisor authority / empowerment	✓	✓		✓				✓
Environment	✓	✓		✓				✓
Commitment to arranging & control		✓						
Project mission / common objective direction	✓	✓				✓		✓
Top administration support	✓	✓				✓	✓	
Client interview / acceptance	✓	✓		✓				
Monitor execution and feedback	✓	✓						
Personnel / teamwork	✓	✓					✓	✓
Technical assignment ability	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓
Trouble shooting / risk management	✓	✓						
Project ownership	✓	✓					✓	
Urgency of project							✓	✓
Duration and measure of project		✓		✓				

Corporate understanding				√		√	√	
-------------------------	--	--	--	---	--	---	---	--

Table2. Responses held by the respondents for Type of project and position

Type of project	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
New product development	22	32.8	32.8
New process introduction	11	16.4	49.2
Quality improvement	7	10.4	59.6
Operational improvement	5	7.4	67
Project transmit	10	14.9	81.9
Others	8	11.9	93.8
Technology transmit	4	5.9	100.0
Total	67	100.0	

Design of study

This study was performed by using an organized questionnaire. As cited by (Sekaran, 2003), “questionnaire could be a widespread technique of collecting information since analysts can assemble data reasonably effectively and the survey reactions are effortlessly coded”. The questionnaire utilized is embraced from Pinto’s project Usage Profile (P.I.P), which has been confirmed to be solid (Pinto, 1986). The questionnaires were dispersed in three ways. The primary way was through electronic mail were added up to 89 E-mails were sent to persons working in industrial companies. Furthermore, and about 320 hard copies of questionnaires were sent to 40 industrial companies.

The targeted industrial companies were from different businesses like gas and petroleum industries, metal items, hardware, apparatus, paper-based Industry, plastic-based industry, material and piece of clothing, and rubber-based industry. In conclusion, a total of 60 messages by fax were sent to the HR section of industrial companies to look for authorization and they are intrigued to take part in the survey.

About 67 respondents were successful in response to the questionnaire and a reaction rate of 14 % was gotten. 86% were unsuccessful to reply and the reason for the remaining non-respondents was obscure. The unit of examination of this study could be extended, which has been completed and classified as a fruitful project within the industrial organization of the respondents.

In this study, the dependent variable is project success in an industrial environment. The dependent variable is measured utilizing 12 things received from the Project Implementation Profile (P.I.P) by Pinto (1986). All things would be evaluated employing a 5-point Likert scale with 1 performing strongly disagree to 5

performing strongly agree. The 10 independent variables are measured by utilizing things included from the Project Implementation Profile (P.I.P) designed by Pinto (1986). All items are moreover evaluated employing a 5-point Likert scale with 1 performing strongly disagree to 5 speaking to strongly agree.

Analysis of variables

In this study, the variables were analyzed by using the SPSS program, the first analysis was factor analysis on the dependent variable, which is project success, and 10 independent variables (table3)

Table 3. Factors and rotated factors for the dependent variable.

Items	Factors	
	1	2
S5 The project was utilized by its aiming clients.	<u>.748</u>	
S3 The project that has been created works.	<u>.645</u>	
S6 Imperative clients, straightforwardly influenced by the venture, made utilize of it.	<u>.568</u>	
*S4 The project has specifically profited the planning users.	<u>.658</u>	.415
S12 The comes about of the project spoke to a clear advancement in performance.		<u>.678</u>
*S7 The project appears to do the leading work in tackling the expecting problem	.491	<u>.798</u>
S11 The project has made a positive effect on those who make utilize of it.		<u>.749</u>
*S10 The project has specifically led to progressed choice-making or performance.	.499	<u>.614</u>
Eigenvalue	2.49	2.23
Percentage of Variance	37.65	15.7
		6
The mark (*) means the factor is cross-loading.		

The varimax rotation technique was utilized to decide any basic components for each variable. The project's success was separated into two primary dimensions. First, the project's success was measured based on its capacity to operate and fulfill the direct clients. The moment measurement of project success was measured based on the benefits realized by the organization. Factor 1 was identified as Direct Project Success and Factor 2 was identified as Indirect Project Success. Coordinate project success since success is measured by the value the project conveys to its direct conclusion clients and indirect project success since success is measured by the value the project conveys to the indirect clients which is the company itself.

Factor analysis was carried out on the 10 independent variables also, these 10 independent variables were classified into 9 factors and each factor has questions of the questionnaire.

Factor 1 which was project arrange observing comprised 5 questions (Q12, Q13, Q14, Q21, Q44) with factor loadings extending from 0.542 to 0.611.

Factor 2 which was client consultation comprised 4 questions (Q16, Q17, Q19, Q43) with factor loadings extending from 0.791 to 0.923.

Factor 3 which was specialized errands comprise of 3 questions (Q31, Q32, Q34) where factor loadings extending from 0.584 to 0.702.

Factor 4 was the best administration bolster with 4 things (Q7, Q9, Q10, Q11) with factor loadings from 0.643 to 0.857.

Factor 5 which was faculty comprised 5 questions (Q18, Q26, Q27, Q28), and the factor stacking extended from 0.545 to 0.677.

Factor 6 was project mission and comprised of 4 questions (Q2, Q3, Q4, Q8) with figure loadings from 0.604 to 0.898.

Factor 7 was client acknowledgment with 3 questions (Q22, Q35, Q36), and the calculate loadings extended from 0.541 to 0.676.

Factor 8 (inconvenience shooting) comprised 2 things (Q47, Q51) with factor loadings of 0.697 and 0.813, and finally, factor 9, which was communication, comprised 2 things (Q42, Q46) with figure loadings 0.605 and 0.639, separately.

Hypotheses test

Perception from the model appeared that High bolster from the best administration had a significant relationship with direct project prepare at 0.10 significance level and the relationship was positive (Beta = 0.314, $p < 0.10$). Furthermore, Competent project staff moreover illustrated a significant positive relationship at 0.05 significance level with direct project preparation (Beta = 0.245, $p < 0.05$). Additionally, In any case, all other factors were found not to have any significant relationship with small direct project success, with these results, it was hence concluded that H1a and H5a are supported.

The model appeared that Recurrent checking and feedback action and Competent project staff have a significant relationship with large direct project prepare and their relationships were positive (Beta = 0.254, $p < 0.05$ for Recurrent checking and feedback action and Beta = 0.261, $p < 0.10$ for Competent project staff). All other 6 factors were found not to have any significant relationship with large direct project success. It was hence concluded that H5b and H6b were supported at 0.10 and 0.05 significant levels, respectively.

Table4: Regression Analysis for the Hypothesis test

H1,2,3,4,5,6a			H1,2,3,4,5,6b	
Independent Variables	Standard Beta		Independent Variables	Standard Beta
High best administration	0.027		High best administration	0.275**
client discussion	-0.085		client discussion	0.074
specialized tasks	-0.007		specialized tasks	0.091
client approval	-0.081		client approval	-0.028
Competent project staff	0.345**		Competent project staff	0.278*
Recurrent checking and feedback action	0.286		Recurrent checking and feedback action	0.005
Successful and suitable communication	-0.086		Successful and suitable communication	-0.029
R2	0.207		R2	0.214
Significant F change	0.043		Significant F change	0.015
* $p < 0.10$			** $p < 0.05$	
*** $p < 0.01$				

Discussion

From the statistical analysis, it was findings that project success isn't in one measurement, typically in line with past researchers' results such as Shenhar (1997), Pinto (1986), and Atkinson (1999). This study has distinguished two primary measurements of project success, the primary measurement is success measured by the effect on the conclusion client or customer. A fruitful industry-based project was measured by the utilization level of its expecting clients, the clients' selection in their everyday assignments, and the

recognition of the clients that the created project works. The moment dimension is success measured by the effect on the company. These impacts can be within the shape of moved forward organizational execution and choice-making preparation at the organizational level and also, the positive effect that the project has on the partners of the project.

The statistical findings illustrated that recurrent checking and feedback action is strongly related to both direct and indirect project success. This finding connects with Pinto and Slevin (1989) results, which stated that recurrent checking and feedback action is the foremost vital factor related to project success over the whole project life cycle. Beginning clarity of objectives and course of the project are imperative components for fruitful projects within the industry fields. It is vital that the objectives of the projects are in line with the common objectives of the company and are made clear to the project group or team. Subsequently, the project group is well mindful and able to distinguish the useful results of the project from the company.

The results appeared that High bolster from the best administration is positively related to indirect project success in an industry which is in line with the results of Kerzner (1987) that a project is likely to be successful on the off chance that obvious bolster and commitment are shown from the top and official administration. This result is additionally bolstered by Belassi and Tukul's results (1996) where 21% of the project supervisors from the industry segment rank high bolster from the best administration as the moment most vital factor for project success. High administration bolster is regularly within the shape of giving adequate resources for the success of the project, sharing duties with the project group, communicating with project group specialists and responsibilities, and supporting the project group in times of emergency or in startling situations.

Statistical results illustrated that recurrent and high client discussion isn't related to project success. The results don't bolster prior researchers' results (Kerzner, 1987; Clarke, 1999) which reported that commitment to early project arranging, execution, and control over the project emphatically impact the success of a project. A perception from the descriptive analysis appeared that a larger part of the sort of project (32.9%) is modern item advancement. In this study, it was found that client discussion isn't significant to project success in the industry. Be that as it may, this finding negates with a researcher like Urban et al. (1993) which expressed that the foremost imperative factor within the success of modern item advancement is to get the voice of the client. It was found that client discussion is more persuasive in service-oriented projects such as data innovation (Tukul and Rom, 2001) and marketing of projects.

The results of this study uncovered that competent project staff is significant to direct project success. A competent project group comprised a project pioneer with its individuals, who are particularly chosen, prepared, and had the specified abilities, information and encounter to handle the requests of the project. When

the project is completed and afterward being presented to the clients or conclusion clients, the capacity of the group individuals to persuade and offer the benefits of the project is imperative to guarantee that the project is promptly acknowledged by the clients. The results from this study are additionally in line with Cooke-Davies (2002) who reported that individuals are included in every prepare and human measurements exist in about all basic factors related to the project success counting the obligation to decide the sufficiency of each prepare that has been carried out.

The accessibility of specialized tasks was found not to be related to project success in the industry. This is often not in line with the results of Pinto and Slevin (1989) that demonstrated the accessibility of a group with relevant technical abilities and the accessibility of the desired innovation are imperative for unused item presentation projects. The conceivable reasons for such results in this study where accessibility of specialized assignments was not a significant factor might be due to the larger part of the respondents from this study (37 %) are from multi-national companies.

The statistical findings appeared that high client approval was not related to project success. The reason was the respondents comprised project pioneers and an individual, in this manner does not represent the voice of the clients for which the project was outlined. In expansion, larger parts of the respondents were reacting to innovation-based projects where time to advertise is regularly the major concern.

Successful and suitable communication was found not related to project success. One of the reasons for this finding may be that this component is as of now implanted and weaved within the success factors. Let us see at project mission where clear project targets and headings are made known to the project group through a few frames of communication. Other than that, best administration illustrates bolster through communication to the project by responding to the resource needs asked by the group. The communication component is additionally shown within the staff and client approval factor, success factors such as competent project staff, best administration bolster, and client discussion lead to project success in the industry as thinks about by Belout (1998), Clarke (1999), Cooke- Davies (2002) and Canister and Heiser (2004). The factors which are empirically bolstered are best administration bolster, client discussion, and competent project staff.

Conclusion

This study illustrated that success factors have undoubtedly advanced agreeing to the sort of project and the environment that the project is working. This can be due to the energetic commerce environment that organizations are working in these days. Whereas success factors have advanced over time, the three factors distinguished in the past two decades still play significant parts in guaranteeing project success in industry

division. These three factors are best administration bolster, client discussion, and competent project staff of the project group.

References

1. Atkinson, R (1999). Project management: cost, time and quality, two best guesses and a phenomenon, its time to accept other success criteria. *Int. J. Project Manage.*,17(6): 337 – 342.
2. Baccarini D (1999). The logical framework method for defining project success. *Project Management Journal*, 30(4): 25 –32.
3. Belassi W, Tukel OI (1996). A new framework for determining critical success/failure factors in projects. *Int. J. Project Manage.*, 14(3), 141– 152.
4. Belout A (1998). Effects of human resource management on project effectiveness and success: Toward a new conceptual framework. *Int. J. Project Manage*, 16(1): 21 – 26.
5. Clarke A (1999). A practical use of key success factors to improve the effectiveness of project management. *Int. J. Project Manage.*, 17(3): 139 – 145
6. Cooke-Davies T (2002). The “real” success factors in projects. *Int. J. of Project Manage*, 6(3): 164 – 170
7. Jugdev K, Muller R (2005). A retrospective look at our evolving understanding project success. *Project Management Journal*, 36(4): 19 – 31
8. Mobey A, Parker D (2002). Risk evaluation and its importance to project implementation. *Int. J. Productivity and Performance Manage.*, 51(4): 202 – 208.
9. Muller R (2003). Communication of information technology project sponsors and sellers in buyer-seller relationships. (Doctorate dissertation, Henley Management College, 2003).
10. Muller R, Turner JR (2003). On the nature of the project as a temporary organization. *Int. J. Project Manage*, 21(1): 1
11. Muller R, Turner JR (2005). The project manager’s leadership style as a success factor on projects: A literature review. *Project Management Journal*,36(2): 49 - 61
12. Pinto JK. (1986). Project Implementation: A determination of its critical success factors, moderators, and their relative importance across the project life cycle (Doctorate dissertation, University of Pittsburgh, 1986).
13. Pinto JK., Slevin PS (1987). Balancing strategy and tactics in project implementation. *ABI/INFORM*, 33 – 40
14. Pinto JK, Slevin PS (1989). Critical success factors in R & D projects. *Research Technology Management*, 32(1): 31 – 36
15. Sekaran Uma (2003). *Research Methods For Business* (4th ed.). New York: John Wiley and Sons
16. Shenhar AJ, Levy O, Dvir D (1997). Mapping the dimensions of project success. *Project Manage. J.*, 28(2): 5 – 13
17. Tukel OI, Rom WO (2001). An empirical investigation of project evaluation criteria. *Int. J. Operations and Production Manage.*, 21(3), 400 – 409
18. Urban GL, Hauser JR (1993). *Design and Marketing of New Products* (2nd ed.). New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
19. Wateridge JF (1995). IT projects: A basis for success. *Int. J. Project Manage.*, 13(3), 169 – 172

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

